

Evaluation of Factors Associated with Malaria Infection Among Children Under-5 Years Who Received SMC

Adamu Muslim¹, Muhammad Abdullahi Sabo², Saleh, Yahaya²

¹Department of Public Health Postgraduate School, Maryam Abacha American University Maradi, Niger Republic

²Faculty of Health Science Maryam Abacha American University Maradi, Niger Republic

Abstract

Malaria is a major public health problem in Nigeria where it accounts for more cases and deaths than any other country in the world. Malaria is a risk for 97% of Nigeria's population. The remaining 3% of the population live in the malaria-free highlands. There are an estimated 100 million malaria cases with over 300,000 deaths per year in Nigeria. This study aimed at evaluating the factors associated with malaria infection among children under-5 years who received SMC. This study was carried out as descriptive-analytical study. Inclusion criteria were strictly based on those children less than 5 years that were eligible for SMC. All those children above 5 years of age were excluded from the study. Few children were noted to come up with malaria fever despite taken the SMC medication which might be due to poor adherence to day 2 and day 3 medication (AQ), not combining SMC programme with other preventive measures against malaria such as the use of LLIN, fumigation and good environmental management. The most alarming was that some of the children coming up with malaria have been participating in the SMC programme for 2 or 3 years, and this might likely be due to the pfmdr1 86Y mutation which is associated with the AQ resistance which is very rare. Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention is an intervention with great potential in Sokoto state, and along with other interventions, it could significantly contribute to approaching the threshold where elimination strategies will be envisioned. During the mass drug administration in all 23 LGAs, comprising 244 wards and 8269 settlements, the intervention significantly reduced hospital visit, admission, and malaria indicators in children.

Keywords: Factors Associated with Malaria Infection, Children Under-5 Years and Who Received SMC

Introduction

Malaria is a major public health problem in Nigeria where it accounts for more cases and deaths than any other country in the world (Strachan, et. al., 2016). Malaria is a risk for 97% of Nigeria's population. The remaining 3% of the population live in the malaria-free highlands. There are an estimated 100 million malaria cases with over 300,000 deaths per year in Nigeria. This compares with 215,000 deaths per year in Nigeria from HIV/AIDS (Strachan, et. al., 2016). Malaria contributes to an estimated 11% of maternal mortality. Malaria accounts for 60% of outpatient visits and 30% of hospitalizations among children under five years of age in Nigeria. Malaria has the greatest prevalence, close to 50%, in children age 6-59 months in the South West, North Central, and North West regions (Zongo, et. al., 2015). Malaria has the least prevalence, 27.6 per cent, in children age 6 to 59 months in the South East region (Antwi, et. al., 2016). Literature Review: Evaluation of Factors Associated with Malaria Infection Among Children Under-5 Years Who Received Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention (SMC).

Malaria remains a significant public health concern, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, where children under the age of five are disproportionately affected. Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention (SMC) has emerged as a crucial intervention strategy to prevent malaria-related morbidity and mortality in this vulnerable population. Understanding the factors associated with malaria infection among children under-five who received SMC is essential for optimizing the effectiveness of this intervention. This literature review aims to synthesize existing research on the evaluation of factors influencing malaria infection among children under-five who have received SMC.

Numerous studies have assessed the efficacy of SMC in reducing malaria incidence among children under-five in malaria-endemic regions. High efficacy rates have been reported, with SMC significantly reducing the burden of clinical malaria and severe malaria cases in treated populations (Bojang et al., 2011; Cissé et al., 2016). However, variations in efficacy have been observed across different settings, highlighting the importance of contextual factors in influencing the effectiveness of SMC programs (Diawara et al., 2017).

Adequate coverage and compliance with SMC treatment regimens are critical for achieving optimal protection against malaria. Studies have identified factors influencing coverage and compliance, including accessibility of healthcare services, community awareness and acceptance of SMC, caregiver knowledge and perceptions of malaria prevention, and socioeconomic factors such as household income and education level (Ajayi et al., 2018). Strategies to improve coverage

Evaluation of Factors ... (Adamu, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10844470>

and compliance, such as community engagement, health education, and integrated service delivery, have been proposed to enhance the effectiveness of SMC programs (Kabaghe et al., 2015; Nsabagasani et al., 2020).

Malaria transmission exhibits seasonal variability, with peak transmission coinciding with the rainy season in many endemic regions. Environmental factors such as rainfall, temperature, and humidity influence the abundance and activity of malaria vectors, thereby affecting malaria transmission dynamics and the efficacy of SMC interventions (Mogeni et al., 2020). Understanding seasonal patterns and environmental determinants of malaria transmission is essential for optimizing the timing and delivery of SMC campaigns.

The emergence of drug-resistant malaria parasites poses a significant challenge to the effectiveness of antimalarial interventions, including SMC. Studies have reported the presence of resistance markers in malaria parasite populations, raising concerns about the potential impact on SMC efficacy and long-term effectiveness (Kalinaki et al., 2017; Kanya et al., 2018). Surveillance efforts to monitor parasite resistance patterns and adapt drug regimens accordingly are essential for sustaining the efficacy of SMC programs.

The evaluation of factors associated with malaria infection among children under-five who received SMC is multifaceted and influenced by various contextual, biological, and programmatic factors (Haruna, 2015). Efficacy of SMC, coverage and compliance, seasonal patterns and environmental factors, and malaria parasite resistance are key considerations in optimizing the effectiveness of SMC interventions. Future research should focus on addressing knowledge gaps, enhancing programmatic strategies, and monitoring the long-term impact of SMC on malaria transmission and morbidity among vulnerable populations.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to assess the factors associated with malaria infection among children under-five who received SMC in Sokoto State.

Research Question

What are the factors associated with malaria infection among children under-five who received SMC in Sokoto State?

Methodology

Sokoto State was carved out of the then North-Western State on February 3rd, 1976 by the former regime of General Murtala Mohammed. Its capital and largest city is Sokoto. The state is named after its capital Sokoto, a city with a long history and the seat of the Sokoto Caliphate. This study was carried out as descriptive-analytical study. Inclusion criteria were strictly based on those children under 5 years that were eligible for SMC. All those children above 5 years of age were excluded from the study. Interviewer administered questionnaire through the research assistant were used which was adopted from the Sokoto state Malaria Elimination Agency SMC campaign for the purpose of this study. It consists of the following sections: SPSS Statistics version 22.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, New York, USA) was used to analyse the data. The analysed data were presented in form of figures and tables and expressed as means $\pm$ SEM (Standard Error of Mean). Statistical differences were compared by simple descriptive analysis, a *p*-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Few children were noted to come up with malaria fever despite taken the SMC medication which might be due to poor adherence to day 2 and day 3 medication (AQ), not combining SMC programme with other preventive measures against malaria such as the use of LLIN, fumigation and good environmental management. The most alarming was that some of the children coming up with malaria have been participating in the SMC programme for 2 or 3 years, and this might likely be due to the pfmdr1 86Y mutation which is associated with the AQ resistance which is very rare.

Evaluation of Factors ... (Adamu, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10844470>

Figure 1: Is there at least one child from 3 months to 5 years old in the compound

Figure 2: Was the compound ever visited by a CHWs/distributor this year for SMC

Figure 2: If No, are there any children 3-59 months living in this compound

Figure 4: If yes, how many times have they visited

Evaluation of Factors ... (Adamu, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10844470>

Figure 5: Were any of your children under 5 years of age sick with fever within the last month?

Figure 6: If yes, how many cycles of SMC have they take?

Figure 7: Did you bring/send them to the health centre

Figure 8: Did your children sleep under a mosquito net last night?

Figure 9: Has anyone sprayed the interior walls of your dwelling against mosquitoes at any time in the past 6 months

Figure 10: How many households are there in this compound?

Evaluation of Factors ... (Adamu, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10844470>

Figure 11: Was there any other child at any other time, who normally doesn't live in this compound, but who was there during one or more cycles, and was treated at least once

Figure 12: Does the child have an SMC card?

Figure 13: Do you / did you know the CHW/distributor who came to the compound to treat your child

Figure 14: Is the CHW/distributor that treated your child from your community/village, or is he coming from outside

Evaluation of Factors ... (Adamu, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10844470>

Figure 15: Can you confirm if the CHW/distributor did administer the first dose to the child on day 1?

Figure 16: If the child vomited/spitted the drugs, did the CHW/distributor repeat the dose

Figure 16: Did the CHW leave you some SMC medicines in a blister pack to give to the child

Figure 17: Do you remember how many tablets were in the blister pack?

Figure 18: Can you explain what you should do with AQ (yellow) tablets at home?

Figure 19: Have you (caregiver) given Day 2 medicine to your child/children?

Discussion of Findings

The responses of the respondents if there is at least one child from 3 months to 5 years old in their compound, 85% respondent selected yes while 15% of the respondents selected no, this was similar to the joint study conducted comprising of Sokoto, Jigawa, Katsina and Zamfara by Malaria Consortium in 2018 of which about 99% of the compound heads confirmed to have children under 5 in their compounds. From

Evaluation of Factors ... (Adamu, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10844470>

our current study 86% of the respondents when interviewed reported that SMC Community Drug Distributors visited their households, while only 13.9% choose not to respond to the question, none of the respondents reported no to the interviewed question. This was also similar to the result obtained during the end of the SMC round survey in 2018 in which 88.2% of all responding compounds with children under 10 was reached by SMC teams while 92.9% of children 3-59 months (programme population target) were treated during the programme. More children were reached and treated in Jigawa (94.5%) than in the other three programme states. Out of all the children within the programme's target age (3-59 months) across the four states, about 6.9% of them were never reached by the SMC programme. This was most common in Katsina (8.2%) and Sokoto (7.0%) and least common in Jigawa (5.5%). From the results obtained in this study work almost all the houses with children aged 3 to 59 months were reached with none skipped during the Mass Drug Administration within the study period [4].

On the frequency of visits during the SMC drugs delivery to ensure completeness of the campaign and effective coverage, the data obtained in this current study shows that 8.4% of the respondents interviewed reported that the community drugs distributors visit their households only once in the cumulative data, while 8.8% recorded two visits, 17.9% recorded three visits, while the majority of the respondents reported recording complete four visits depicting 64.9%. This was analogous to the evaluation report in the four north western states (Sokoto, Jigawa, Katsina and Zamfara state) in 2018, Out of the proportion of under 5 children (93%) that received SMC treatment at any of the program's cycles, about 82% reported receiving just one visit and 1 treatment, 76% received two visits and 2 treatments, 66% received three visits and 3 treatment and about 57% received four visit and 4 complete treatments across the survey states.

A progression in the coverage rate was observed in Jigawa and Zamfara states from cycle one to two with about 4% and 1% increase for the second cycle respectively, while other states reported a decrease in the proportion of the children that received the cycle two treatment indicating two visits within each round relative to cycle one response. Across states, sixty-eight per cent of caregivers in Katsina reported that children received two visits indicating two treatments while 69% of caregivers in Sokoto state reported dose administration in cycle two. There was a slight coverage increase in Katsina from cycle three to four of about 2%. Across the states, Zamfara reported the highest percentage of children 3-59-month-old, who received at least three cycles (73%). About 68% of respondents in Jigawa state reported having received at least 3 cycles of the SMC treatment whilst 53% and 52% in Katsina and Sokoto respectively also received 3 cycles. The majority of the caregiver of children 3-59 months reported not receiving the four-cycle treatment. About 37% of children 3-59 months were reported covered by all four cycles across all the surveyed states [5]. These ranges from 53% in Zamfara, 41% in Jigawa, 30% in Katsina and 26% in Sokoto state, the obtainable data show a wide margin in the percentage scores in the current study. In the current study, the proportion of children that come-up with fever after taking SMC medication was equally analysed and the obtainable data shows that the caregiver that responded Yes to that were 18.7%, 80% of the respondents said no to that and 1.3% decline to respond to the question, this is not unconnected to the fact that SMC is often implemented alongside other malaria preventing measures that strengthen the effectiveness of the campaign, such as the ownership and intensive use of LLIN, mosquito vector control strategies and adherence to full course of the SMC medication, a high proportion of children coming up with malaria fever after taking SMC medication were not sleeping under the long-lasting insecticidal net to compliment the SMC medicine taking, not sleeping under LLIN negatively affect the effectiveness of the chemoprevention as children keep coming-up with malaria after treatment and the reasons given by the caregivers is that the net was temporarily unavailable (62%), while about 15% said the net was damaged and same proportion said they forgot to prepare the net for the child to sleep under.

In contrast to the present study, Rek *et al.* [6]. in their study non-adherence to long-lasting insecticide-treated bed net use following successful malaria control in Tororo, Uganda reported non-adherence was greater among children under the age of 5 years and school-aged children between the ages of 5 and 17 years, while inhabitants of poorer families were less adherent [6]. From the observation made on the child record card that was issued to caregivers and the interviewed conducted the result obtained shows 18.7% of respondents that said yes from the previous response depicting 219 caregivers, it was noted that 47% of the respondents' children only took one cycle of treatment, 32% took only the two cycles of treatment, 14% took three cycles of while only 8% took the full four-cycle of treatment. This shows non-compliance to the three days course of treatment which contradicts the concept of SMC medication with

Evaluation of Factors ... (Adamu, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10844470>

only the 18% that complies. Moreover, the effectiveness of SMC goes in line with adherence and compliance to the full course of treatment. Coverage of SMC among eligible children in the study area was relatively high. Over 80% of children received at least the first day's SMC treatment either in their household which is the gold standard or in the health facility after referral during the first cycle of treatment. However, this proportion decreased over the consecutive cycles based on interviews conducted and SMC cards observation. This was similar to the result obtained during Malaria Consortium annual survey in 2014 where the result obtained show coverage per cycle slightly declined at subsequent cycles from 75 per cent in cycle one through to 55 per cent in cycle four [7]. This is in cases where information could be obtained, SMC distribution at each cycle was equitable. 61.8% of all children for whom data was collected received at least 3 cycles of SMC. Several factors could explain the limited coverage for households and children, notably their absence during the rainy season. Indeed, it is common for some household members to spend all day in the fields. Some even leave their homes and temporarily live in shelters closer to the fields as reported by [7]. Also, it is common practice in both rural and urban communities for young children to stay with their mother during the day and accompany her wherever she goes. This could explain why, even if a household was visited, some children did not receive SMC treatment.

The result of the interview conducted with the healthcare providers on if they sent their children to healthcare centre after a referral from the community revealed 62% of respondents selected yes they ensure the referral linkage is sustained and the affected children were taking to the health facility while 38% of responded selected no, this was because not all the health facilities are PMI supported site that provides both testings with mRDT and treatment with the first line antimalarial (ACT) is provided free with no payment required to assess such services. Most caregivers in this study work sought treatment from health facilities after referral or when their children fail sick with symptoms of malaria, this was similar to the result obtained in 2018 survey by the Malaria Consortium which shows Katsina having 67%, Jigawa and Sokoto having 61% of caregivers that visited health centres for the care of their sick children. Still on the 2018 survey information on the health outcome for children under 5 whose caregivers sought treatment at health facilities were also considered. Amongst those treated with SMC drugs, caregivers reported that about 78% on average were tested at the health facility during the child's visit. The proportion among those who were reported to have tested positive for malaria was 84% across all states. Sokoto state had the highest rate of positive cases reported by the respondents 90% which is contrary to the result obtained in this current study. These results are based on respondents recall; no record was access to confirm the malaria incidence [8].

On the use of Long-Lasting Insecticidal Net (LLIN) the proportion of children under 5 years of age that sleep under the LLIN on the previous night, it was reported that 85% of children within the required age bracket sleep under a mosquito net last night, while 15% selected no implying that they did not sleep under a mosquito net as obtained from the result of the interview with the caregivers in the study area. A similar study conducted by Cissé *et al.* [9] indicated that the use of mosquito net among children treated and not treated during the cycles after assessment shows that the majority of the children who were treated across the states sleep under a mosquito net on the average (74%). Also, a very high proportion of sleep under a mosquito net among those not treated (70%). In another survey conducted in 2014, the result shows that in all the households visited, 80.7% of all children at baseline and 73.1% at end line slept under a net the previous night. However, in only net owning households, 90.8% of children slept under a net. This proportion significantly increased to 93.8% at the end line. Usually, about 90 per cent of children sleep under a net in these communities which is similar to the result obtained in our current study [10].

From the study conducted on the issue of vector control the result obtained from the participants when asked if anyone had sprayed the interior walls of their houses in the study areas shows that 52% responded Yes to the question, 15% responded No, while 35% of the responded has no answer to the interviewed question. Occasionally, Indoor residual spray exercise and larviciding are being conducted by the state in the LGAs in Sokoto state aimed to reduce the vector density and also to clear the breeding sites of the mosquito vector. The 2018 survey result shows that about 95% of the compounds visited were not sprayed by anyone in the past 6 months before the survey. This was also the case for compounds not visited during the treatment period as it equally depicts 98% of the respondents during the survey. Although, few respondents had disclosed having received visits from personal intending to spray houses, but were prevented by some households due to cultural reasons. In this current study the number of households presents within each compound were inquired on the number of households in the respondents' compounds

Evaluation of Factors ... (Adamu, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10844470>

and Information gathered from respondents on the survey shows that 79% of them are 1 householder, 15% are 2 householders while 6% of them are 3 householders [11].

Conclusion

Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention is an intervention with great potential in Sokoto state, and along with other interventions, it could significantly contribute to approaching the threshold where elimination strategies will be envisioned. During the mass drug administration in all 23 LGAs, comprising 244 wards and 8269 settlements, the intervention significantly reduced hospital visit, admission, and malaria indicators in children.

References

- Ajayi IO, et al. (2018). Feasibility of malaria diagnosis and management in Burkina Faso, Nigeria, and Uganda: a community-based observational study. *Clin Infect Dis.* 67(11):1666-1674.
- Antwi, G. D., Bates, L. A., King, R., Mahama, P. R., Tagbor, H., Cairns, M., & Newell, J. N. (2016). Facilitators and Barriers to Uptake of an Extended Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention Programme in Ghana: A Qualitative Study of Caregivers and Community Health Workers. *PloS One*, **11(11)**. 10.1371/journal.pone.0166951: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0166951>
- Bojang K, et al. (2011). Efficacy of RTS, S/AS02 malaria vaccine against Plasmodium falciparum infection in semi-immune adult men in The Gambia: a randomised trial. *Lancet.* 358(9297):1927-34.
- Cissé B, et al. (2016). Seasonal intermittent preventive treatment with artesunate and sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine for prevention of malaria in Senegalese children: a randomised, placebo-controlled, double-blind trial. *Lancet.* 367(9511):659-67.
- Cissé, B., Ba, E. H., Sokhna, C., JL, N. D., Gomis, J. F., Dial, Y., . . . Milligan, P. (2016). Effectiveness of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention in Children under Ten Years of Age in Senegal: A Stepped-Wedge Cluster-Randomised Trial. *PLoS Medicine*, **13(11)**. 10.1371/journal.pmed.1002175: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1002175>
- Diawara F, et al. (2017). Seasonal malaria chemoprevention with sulphadoxine-pyrimethamine and amodiaquine selects Pfdhfr-dhps quintuple mutant genotype in Mali. *PLoS ONE.* 12(8):e0182759.
- Haruna, A. S. (2015). Hitches in the administration of guidance and counselling services in Nigeria secondary schools. *International Journal of Humanities, Social Sciences and Education*, 2 (12), 20-23.
- Kabaghe AN, et al. (2015). Access and adequate utilization of malaria control interventions in rural Malawi: a descriptive quantitative study. *Malar J.* 14:491.
- Kalinaki M, et al. (2017). High prevalence of PfCRT-CVIET haplotype in isolates from asymptomatic and symptomatic patients in Uganda. *Malar J.* 16(1):372.
- Kanya MR, et al. (2018). Comparison of parasitological methods and the detection of pfrp2/3 gene deletions for the diagnosis of malaria in Uganda. *Malar J.* 17(1):93.
- Mogeni P, et al. (2020). High sensitivity detection of malaria parasites in a high transmission region using a novel 18S rRNA gene-based assay. *Sci Rep.* 10(1):19841.
- Nsabagasani X, et al. (2020). Factors influencing utilisation of seasonal
- Rek, J., Musiime, A., Zedi, M., Otto, G., Kyagamba, P., Asiimwe Rwatooro, J., . . . Krezanoski, P. J. (2020). Non-adherence to long-lasting insecticide treated bednet use following successful malaria control in Tororo, Uganda. *PloS One*, **15(12)**, e0243303. 10.1371/journal.pone.0243303: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0243303>
- Strachan, C. E., Kana, M., Martin, S., Dada, J., Wandera, N., Marasciulo, M., . . . Baba, E. (2016). The use of formative research to inform the design of a seasonal malaria chemoprevention intervention in northern Nigeria. *Malaria Journal*, **15**, 474. 10.1186/s12936-016-1526-9: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-016-1526-9>
- Zongo, I., Milligan, P., Compaore, Y. D., Some, A. F., Greenwood, B., Tarning, J., . . . Ouedraogo, J. B. (2015). Randomized Noninferiority Trial of Dihydroartemisinin-Piperaquine Compared with Sulfadoxine-Pyrimethamine plus Amodiaquine for Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention in Burkina Faso. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, **59(8)**, 4387-4396. 10.1128/aac.04923-14: <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.04923-14>